

Resurrecting Eco Spiritual Myth: Understanding the Hidden Message of Amitav Ghosh's Jungle Nama

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Abstract

This paper mainly explores Jungle Nama by Amitav Ghosh from an Eco-spiritual perspective. This long narrative poem deals with certain existing legends which have been a source of strength for the natives of Sundarban since ages. In this work, Amitav Ghosh beautifully captures the spirit of the Jungle which stands as a grand entity inhabited by figures like Bon Bibi, Shah Jangoli, the evil Dokkhin Rai and the sometimes innocent, sometimes ignorant human beings. For the natives, the goddess - Bon Bibi is a saviour and an integral part of their identity. Irrespective of religion, people associate with her and seek solace. She commands respect and generates eco-spiritual values which renders the locals as eco-friendly people. In the current scenario, the third-world countries are struggling to build their post-colonial identity. The aspects of 'Eco-spirituality' as upheld in this work can provide distinctness to the Indian spirit. Also, as a potential theoretical framework, this will generate ideas to the western world for sustainable development.

Keywords: Sundarban, Amitav Ghosh, Bon Bibi, Tigers, Eco-spirituality

Introduction

'Eco-spirituality' is a phenomenon of revering nature as God. Following this perspective, one does not look at the environment from a physical perspective but rather from a metaphysical perspective. It has originated from the Latin word 'Spiritus' which means breath and also symbolizes life. It emphasizes on valuing nature beyond its material things and acknowledges its intrinsic value in life. This idea of equating nature with God creates a spiritual and moral imperative for the protection and conservation of the environment. Indians have respected the supernatural force of nature and worshipped the different units of it as manifestation of God. They even adore several animal forms like cows, elephants, snakes etc. Similarly, plants like Neem, Tulasi, and many more have been included as Gods. Thus, it can be asserted that eco-spirituality as a phenomenon existed in India since ancient times.

Jungle Nama by Amitav Ghosh is a 21st century long narrative poem that evokes ancient myths and legends to induce a consciousness for the past and its rich Eco Spiritual traditions. The word 'Jungle Nama' has its etymological roots in English, Sanskrit, and Persian languages. While the English word 'Jungle' is derived from a Sanskrit root, the word 'Nama' is Persian which means a tale. Thus, *Jungle Nama* is a long narrative poem that glorifies the forest by upholding the several supernatural legends it supports. By presenting all these aspects, Amitav Ghosh hoists the supremacy of the Indian Eco Spiritual ideal to the 21st-century world that laments the degradation of the environment.

Objective and Methodology:

This paper aims to thematically interpret the work- Jungle Nama by Amitav Ghosh to explore the vivid aspects of eco-spiritual philosophy forever

present in the Indian society. In the Twenty-First century, with the world pacing towards to newer developments in the field of technology, Ghosh takes a bold step into the past and resurrects the richness of its tradition. The exploration of this aspect would help Indians to claim their dominance on the newly evolving theory of Eco-spirituality. Indians have always been practitioners of eco-spiritual ideology which is being developed by the western people as an idea to protect the environment. Understanding this rich heritage will not only refresh Indians' adoration for the environment, but also help them to claim their ownership on the discourse. This discourse will further help in uplifting the Indian identity in the post-colonial scenario. For a systematic study, the paper has been divided into three sub-units:

1. Personification of Nature in Jungle-Nama
2. The Ever-present Conflict of Good and Evil.
3. Significance of Eco-spiritual tradition in Twenty-first century.

Personification of Nature in Jungle-Nama:

The work Jungle-Nama treats 'Nature' as an entity with an active consciousness. The Jungle in it is a place that thrives nature, animals and human beings in a dynamic and yet holistic bond. It can be better asserted that the Jungle anchors the existence of all the life forms within it.

Tiger, the main source of terror in the lives of these people is personified by the character of Dokkhin Rai. He loves absolute power and thus terrorizes the people with his earth shaking roars. Amitav Ghosh invokes the original legends about Dokkhin Rai that asserts that "every animal, every ghost and every malevolent spirit of the forest was under the exclusive command of Dokkhin Rai". (Karmar-438). He is projected as a demon king lusting after human blood especially those

belonging to the pure souls. Absolute Control over ignorant and innocent human being had made him so preposterous that he openly challenged Bon Bibi and Shah Jongoli (Divine Beings) for a battle. Such a magnificent presentation of the menacing side of the nature certainly evokes consciousness for its immense power. All the devilish attributes are presented through the image of Dokkhin Rai

Contrary to the character of Dokkhin Rai, Bon Bibi and Shah Jongoli are divine saviours of the people. Bon Bibi is the Mistress of the forest. Her source of strength is her compassion. Shah Jongoli is a divine warrior whose one stroke sends his enemy swiftly flying back. People's faith on Bon Bibi and their worship of her reveals their spiritual inclination towards the environment. The nature acts as a source of terror as well as a saviour for them. Thus, it can be asserted that in this part of the world, nature plays an all-encompassing role in the lives of people

The Ever-Present Conflict of Good and Evil

The work *Jungle Nama* also projects the universal metaphor for the struggle between Good and Evil. The characters- Bon Bibi and Shah Jongoli represent goodness whereas Dokkhin Rai is a representative of the evil in human psyche. Any good act is considered to be a form of worship and also people revere whatever is virtuous. In this part of the world, people pray to celebrate the goodness of Bon Bibi. Perhaps her divinity lies in the fact that despite being a mistress of the forest, she never claims her authority over it like Dokkhin Rai does. Such aspects of eco-spirituality in Indian culture reminds one of the fact that nature is Supreme.

Dhona and Dukhey are the human representative forms of Dokkin Rai and Bon Bibi. Dhona is an egocentric person and wants to exploit the forest of its rich resources like wax, honey and timber. He Bargained for Dukhey's life in exchange of the riches offered by Dokkhin Rai. His deal over Dukhey's life for material wealth presents his lack of respect for the world that sustains him. He stands as a Metaphor for people who compromise with natural resources for the sake of their luxury. Dukhey is a pure and innocent soul. His heart is full of faith. His devotion on God represents human faith on the environment for their lives. According to the major theoretical understanding, he might be considered to be a subaltern character. However, Ghosh presents him as a figure richer than the wealthy and powerful ones. His greatest treasury was his undefeated trust on nature that takes up a Godly proportion here. His belief helps him to surpass the worldly miseries and unite with God. Instead of being treated as a subaltern, Amitav Ghosh presents Dukhey as a 'man of the nature' who is preserved by it.

Significance of Eco-spiritual tradition in Twenty-first century:

Environmental affiliations are not much removed from the complex concept of identity. In the post-colonial context, people are struggling to create their identity by opposing the western dominant ideology on one hand and reiterating their traditions and simple way of living on the other. Environmental concerns are problematic in the post-colonial scenario. In the first place, it is the western pattern of living that has led to the crisis. Apart from *Jungle Nama*, other works by poets like Desmond Kharmawphlang, Kynphan SingNongkynrih and many more also prove that the traditional ways of life have been simpler. The lifestyle was sustainable as people shared a correlative bond with the environment. It is ironical that in the current times, both environmental degradation and consciousness are promoted by the western world. Their anthropocentric philosophy is uninviting to the indigenous masses who are working under the economic supervision of the western world. To them, the native philosophy of a spiritual bond with the nature is best extended. In such circumstances, aspects of eco-spirituality will communicate acceptable messages on environment. The western world which is trying to formulate eco-spiritual discourse to protect the environment can learn a valuable lesson from the Indian example.

Conclusion:

Amitav Ghosh's work *Jungle Nama* not only rejuvenates the traditional patterns of life, but also generates a deep-regard for its rich heritage. An understanding of this work leaves future scope for research into the dimensions of Indian Eco-spirituality and how it can revolutionize the discourse on environment.

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